

Welcome to the online survey with the developer teams of Base4NFDI basic services!

Technopolis has been commissioned to evaluate Base4NFDI. As you are aware, Base4NFDI is a joint initiative of all NFDI consortia to create shared basic services that can be used by potentially all consortia.

The aim of this survey is to gather insights from the developer teams of basic services on Base4NFDI.

The survey covers topics such as the project structure, processes for identifying and discussing basic services, your assessment of the submission and evaluation processes for basic services, activities for the deployment of basic services and your evaluation of the relevance of the project.

Completing the survey will take approximately 10–20 minutes. Your responses will be used exclusively in an anonymised and aggregated form.

Please complete the questionnaire by April 22nd.

Your perspectives and experiences are crucial for assessing and further developing Base4NFDI. Your input will be a key component of the evaluation report.

In addition to this online survey, further data collection activities will be conducted, including another online survey with individuals affiliated with NFDI consortia, document analyses, interviews, as well as focus groups and workshops.

If you have any questions regarding this survey, please feel free to contact us at dominik.obeth@technopolis-group.com.

We sincerely appreciate your valuable support!

Section A: Survey respondents' affiliations & backgrounds

Mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk (*).

A1. Are you a member of the developer team for the Base4NFDI basic service ?

If you are a member of multiple developer teams and you prefer to answer this survey for another basic service, please select "No" and choose the corresponding basic service in the next question.

Yes

No

A2. Are you part of any other developer team of a Base4NFDI basic service?

If you are part of multiple Base4NFDI developer teams, please select the one for which you would like this survey for.

IAM4NFDI

PID4NFDI

TS4NFDI

Jupyter4NFDI

DMP4NFDI

KGI4NFDI

nfdi.software

RDMTraining4NFDI

I am not part of any Base4NFDI basic service developer team

A3.

A4. Besides being part of the developer team for , are you personally active in any other NFDI consortium/consortia your institution is part of?

Multiple selections possible. Being personally active in a consortium involves, for instance, taking part in consortia meetings or being part of a working group of this consortium.

BERD@NFDI

KonsortSWD

NFDI4Culture

NFDI4Memory

NFDI4Objects

Text+

NFDI4DataScience

NFDI4Energy

NFDI4Ing

NFDIxCS

NFDI-MatWerk

DataPLANT

FAIRagro

GHGA

NFDI4Biodiversity

NFDI4BIOIMAGE

NFDI4Health

NFDI4Immuno

NFDI4Microbiota

DAPHNE4NFDI

FAIRmat

MaRDI

NFDI4Cat

NFDI4Chem

NFDI4Earth

PUNCH4NFDI

I am not personally active in any NFDI consortium

A5. For how long have you been part of the developer team for the Base4NFDI basic service ?

Choose one of the following answers.

Less than half a year

More than half a year, but less than a year

More than a year

Don't know / No answer

Section B: Internal structure and responsibilities of Base4NFDI

B1. Are you generally aware of how Base4NFDI is internally structured to support Basic Service development?

Choose one of the following answers. Internal structures refer, for example, to the Task Areas, Service Stewards, and Section Liaison Officers.

- Yes, definitely
- Somewhat
- Not really
- No, not at all

B2. Have you personally ever been in contact with someone from the Base4NFDI team?

Choose one of the following answers. The Base4NFDI team includes Task Areas 1-4 as well as the Service Stewards.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

B3. Do you know whom to contact within Base4NFDI for your concerns?

Choose one of the following answers

- Yes, always
- Mostly
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- No, not at all

B4.

Who would you most likely contact within Base4NFDI if you have a question or a query about...

If you can think of multiple contacts for any aspect, please select the one you would be most likely to reach out to.

	Service Stewards	Members of TA 1	Members of TA 2	Section Liaison Officers (TA 3)	Base-Office (TA 4)	Contact with someone, but unsure of their role	Members of my developer team	Don't know
the submission process for a basic service proposal	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
decision making processes about basic service submissions (e.g. in the consortia assembly or the Technical Expert Committee)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
questions about the development process or required support for the basic service(s) in which I'm involved (e.g. assuring interoperability with service solutions of consortia)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
outreach activities to promote the deployment and popularity of basic services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
training activities to foster the deployment of basic services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

B5. Do you have any comments or suggestions for improvement regarding the internal structure of Base4NFDI that you would like to point out?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Section C: Submission process

The following questions refer to processes regarding the submission of basic services at Base4NFDI. We refer to submission (processes) as all actions related to writing and submitting a basic service proposal to Base4NFDI for any of the three development phases (initialisation, integration, ramping-up), including re-submissions.

C1. Have you personally been active in any of the following sections of the NFDI (e.g. in a section's working group)?

Select all that apply.

Common Infrastructures (section-infra)

C4.

If you look at the processes for identifying basic services in the sections and the submission process for basic services, how do you personally consider the relative influence of the various actors involved?

	Too little say	Adequate say	Too much say	No say	Don't know
Sections	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Consortium spokespersons	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Consortium member institutions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Technical Expert Committee	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Base4NFDI team	<input type="checkbox"/>				
NFDI scientific senate	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Infrastructure organisations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Researchers from universities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Researchers from research institutes (Max Planck, Leibniz etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C5. Do you have any feedback on the process for identifying, discussing, and submitting potential basic services that you would like to highlight or suggest improvements for?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or German.

Section D: Evaluation processes for basic services at Base4NFDI (Technical Expert Committee)

We refer to the evaluation process as the entire process involved in evaluating basic service submissions at Base4NFDI. This includes the assessment and review of basic service submissions by the Technical Expert Committee (TEC) as well as discussions, votes, and decisions made in the consortia assembly regarding basic services.

D1. Are you generally aware of the TEC and its role in the evaluation process?

Choose one of the following answers.

Yes

Yes, somewhat

No

Don't know / No answer

D2.

To what extent would you agree with the following statements about the evaluation processes for basic services conducted by Base4NFDI together with the Technical Expert Committee (TEC)?

Fully agree Mostly agree Partly agree / partly disagree Mostly disagree Fully disagree Don't know

The criteria applied by the TEC for evaluating basic service submissions are transparent and well-communicated.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The recommendations of the TEC regarding the evaluation of basic service submissions are generally fair.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The evaluation process conducted by Base4NFDI together with the TEC demonstrates subject-matter expertise.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The published reasons for decisions (e.g., acceptance, rejection, required revisions, or budget reductions) are communicated clearly and are understandable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								
The personnel composition of the TEC is adequate to evaluate the technical aspects of the various proposed services effectively.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>								

D3. Do you want to specify your answer to the previous question? (e.g. How could the process be improved? What aspects are working particularly well?)

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

Fully agree Mostly agree Partly agree / partly disagree Mostly disagree Fully disagree Don't know

The evaluation process generally accounts adequately for the needs and requirements of the consortia.

.....

The evaluation process generally contributes to a sustainable deployment and usage of basic services in the long run.

.....

E4. If you look at the processes for evaluating of basic services at Base4NFDI overall, how do you personally consider the relative influence of the various actors involved?

Too little say Adequate say Too much say No say Don't know

Consortium spokespersons

.....

Consortium member institutions

.....

Technical Expert Committee

.....

Base4NFDI team

.....

NFDI scientific senate

.....

E5. Are there any other comments or suggestions for improvement regarding the submission and evaluation processes for basic services that you would like to point out?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

Section F: Activities for service deployment and collaboration between actors and stakeholders

F1. Which of the following activities have you actively organised or are you planning to organise to support the deployment of the basic service in the consortia?

	Already carried out	Planning to carry out	Not yet carried out	Not applicable	Don't know
Communication and outreach activities (e.g., newsletters, or articles to raise awareness about the service).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Networking events or activities (e.g., presentations at conferences, fostering collaborations or creating connections with relevant stakeholders in the consortia and beyond, e.g. EOSC).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Service Roadshows	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Workshops regarding the basic service {AXbasicservice.shown} (e.g., hands-on sessions, demonstrations, or brainstorming events tailored to the service).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Training sessions (e.g., structured learning opportunities or tutorials to enhance skills related to the service).	<input type="checkbox"/>				

F2. How has Base4NFDI supported you in carrying out these activities?

Select all that apply.

- Provided communication materials or templates for outreach (e.g., presentations, newsletters, or promotional content).
- Facilitated networking opportunities with relevant stakeholders or consortia members.
- Offered guidance or co-facilitation for workshops (e.g., technical input, resources, or logistical support).
- Delivered training resources or expertise to support training sessions for the consortia.
- Provided technical or operational support for deployment and user assistance.
- Shared feedback mechanisms or tools to help collect and address user input.
- Offered best practices, guidelines, or strategic advice for consortia engagement.
- Don't know

No answer

Other (please specify).

Other (please specify).

F3. Are there any other materials or support activities that you wish for?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

F4. In which of the following activities have you already taken part as a participant?

Select all that apply.

Networking events or activities (e.g., fostering collaborations or creating connections with relevant stakeholders in the consortia).

Service Roadshows

Base4NFDI User Conference (UC4B)

Demos/Presentations/Lectures about basic services

Interactive formats (Workshops, Q&A, trainings, hands-on sessions)

Interactive meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders

Meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders

Very helpful Rather helpful Partly helpful / partly not helpful Rather not helpful Not helpful at all Don't know

Interactive meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Meetings/conferences/workshops with EOSC stakeholders	<input type="checkbox"/>					

F7. To what extent would you agree with the following statements?

The Base4NFDI team consists of the member of the task areas, the section liaison officers and the service stewards.

Fully agree Mostly agree Partly agree / partly disagree Mostly disagree Fully disagree Don't know

The communication between my developer team and the Base4NFDI team is effective and timely.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The Base4NFDI team is responsive to our questions, requests, and feedback.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The Base4NFDI Team supports us in better understanding the requirements and needs of the consortia.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I always know whom to contact if I have any issues or questions.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Overall, I am satisfied with the collaboration with the Base4NFDI team.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

F8. What specific improvements, if any, would you suggest to enhance the collaboration and communication between your developer team and the Base4NFDI team?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

F9. Regarding the overall collaboration between the developer team for and each consortium: Please indicate approximately to how many consortia the following statements apply:

	No consortium	1-5 consortia	6 – 10 consortia	11 – 15 consortia	16 – 20 consortia	More than 20 consortia	Don't know
Our developer team closely cooperates with the consortium to understand its needs and concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The consortia's feedback can be effectively incorporated into the development of the basic service.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
We obtain clear and binding commitments from the consortium on how it plans to integrate the basic service into their consortium.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Our developer team actively promotes the basic service within the consortium to ensure its adoption and usability.	<input type="checkbox"/>						
The collaboration between our developer team and the consortium is productive and beneficial for deploying the basic service.	<input type="checkbox"/>						

F10. What specific improvements, if any, would you suggest to enhance the collaboration between your developer team and the consortia? If the quality of your collaboration differs between consortia, please specify here.

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

F11. Are there any other aspects you would like to mention regarding the collaboration with the Base4NFDI team?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

Section G: Relevance of Base4NFDI for the community

G1. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?

IAM4NFDI

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

G2. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?

PID4NFDI

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**G3. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
TS4NFDI**

- For the NFDI community as a whole
- For my consortium
- For my institution
- For individual users
- For complementing EOSC services
- I don't know this service
- No answer

**G4. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
Jupyter4NFDI**

- For the NFDI community as a whole
- For my consortium
- For my institution
- For individual users
- For complementing EOSC services
- I don't know this service
- No answer

**G5. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
DMP4NFDI**

- For the NFDI community as a whole
- For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**G6. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
KGI4NFDI**

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**G7. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
nfdi.software**

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

**G8. Which of the following basic services are, from your point of view, in general useful for the following user groups?
RDMTraining4NFDI**

For the NFDI community as a whole

For my consortium

For my institution

For individual users

For complementing EOSC services

I don't know this service

No answer

G9. When you look at all basic services that have been granted funding by Base4NFDI, are there any gaps, i.e. basic services that would be needed, but are not yet being developed?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

H3. How do the services developed under Base4NFDI address the FAIR principles? Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Fully agree	Mostly agree	Partly agree / partly disagree	Mostly don't agree	Don't agree at all	Don't know
The developed services improve the findability of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The developed services improve the accessibility of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The developed services improve the interoperability of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The developed services improve the reusability of data and resources in the NFDI community.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

H4. Are there any other aspects that you would like to mention regarding your overall satisfaction with Base4NFDI?

Optional. You can answer this question in English or in German.

' + '

This survey is specifically targeted towards members of the developer teams of Base4NFDI basic services. If you feel you have received this in error or have any questions, please contact Dominik Obeth (dominik.obeth@technopolis-group.com) for further clarification.

' + '

Thank you for your interest and support! You may close this survey now.

'); } else { document.write('

Your responses have been saved.

' + '

We will conduct in-depth interviews and additional workshops based on the survey results, with the evaluation concluding in August.

' + '

Thank you for your valuable support! You may close this survey now.

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